

AN EVALUATION OF LANGUAGE POLICY IN A BILINGUAL SCHOOL IN JAMBI: BARRIERS OF USING ENGLISH INSTRUCTION

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Abstract

This study aimed to arrive at an assessment of schools' language policy by examining elements related to curriculum; learners' needs, program and course goals, the selection materials and activities, administrators and teachers, and assessment through the collection and analysis qualitative data based on teachers' perspectives in a Jambi Bilingual School (a pseudonym, henceforth referred to JBS), independent bilingual schools in Jambi. Particularly, the purposes of this study were to explore the implementation of English as a language of instruction in a bilingual school and teachers' barriers of teaching contents in one private bilingual school in Jambi city. The study was designed as mixed methods research design (qualitative and quantitative design) with a case study approach, and involved demographic background information, questionnaire, documents, and semi- structured and in- depth interview for data collection. The documents were used to find out the comprehensive overview of the bilingual school program while all of the interviews were used to ask participants to narrate their accounts and perspectives on their barriers in using English as the medium of instruction at a micro (classroom) level. Overall, the findings of this study revealed that the successful implementation of English as a language of instruction in a bilingual school were interrelatedly challenged by several barriers including teacher's attitudes and ability to use English, language policy, teaching materials, students and teachers' English proficiency, curriculum, student assessment, and admission policy. Recommendations for further research are also discussed.

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1. Introduction

Interpretation of the voluminous research on bilingual education has been highly controversial among both academics and policymakers for more than 25 years. In Indonesia, most politicized discussions of bilingual education policy have focused on language minority children. Frequently, their backgrounds in languages other than Indonesian are assumed to be the cause of their educational deficiencies. Many schools in various countries, including Indonesia, offer bilingual education for their pupils. In terms of bilingual education, the growing need for English as a key to global communication, relations, and information, is noticeable in schools around the world. In response to these imperatives of global competitiveness, Indonesian government developed a new act on its educational system in 2003, which; *"the government and local governments shall organize at least a unit of education at all levels of education, to be developed as a unit having international standard of education"* (No. 20, year 2003 on education system, p. 26 – 27). Looking at good opportunities they may derive from the use of the language, many schools have adopted English as a Medium of Instruction (EMI) now. This happens not only in English as a second language (ESL) settings like India, the Philippines, Singapore, Malaysia, Hong Kong, and other Asian countries, but also in countries where English is a foreign language (EFL) like Netherlands, Germany, Hungary, Kuwait, Saudi Arabia, Thailand, and Indonesia. In Indonesia, English as a medium of Instruction (EMI) is no longer a new

phenomenon today. Fast-growing schools like Jakarta International School (JIS), Central International School, British International School, Asian International school, Kanaan Global School, and others are developing international programs using English as a medium of instruction. In response to global challenges, Jambi Bilingual School (JBS), for instance, has outlined in its strategic plans.

Such a program is being offered by JBS, now in its more than ten years operation, the school has its own educational and language goals and curriculum combined with the government regulations. As one of the bilingual schools in Jambi, with bilingualism and intercultural awareness becoming more important in our era of increasing global and intercultural among speakers in different languages, the effectiveness of implementing language policy in the classroom is important to help learning achieving language aims fitted up for lives in interconnected world. However, problems emerge relating to bilingual education. One of the problems in presenting a clear case for the effectiveness of bilingual education results from the confusion program evaluation research. Much of the adverse publicity for bilingual education stems from a set of poor program evaluation results. Many researchers, however, feel that it is virtually impossible to control for all the background variables associated with bilingual education outcomes. A number of variables can have a negative effect on the outcome of a particular bilingual program; the number of qualified bilingual teachers, parental support, administrative support, material resources, time allocation for the child's first language and the second language, the socio- cultural and educational background of the community, and the general school curriculum and climate.

On the other hand, because bilingual education has become an ideological lightning rod that tends to attract groups with a variety of pedagogical agendas, language-minority educators have no choice whereas to become better informed and engaged in the language policy debate. To hold their ground in the debate, however, they must have a clearly articulated strategy for addressing language issues within a political context to multiple publics. Crawford [2000b, p. 124] suggests that "educators must learn to participate more effectively in the policy debate: not by distorting evidence or by denouncing their opponents as racists, but by explaining bilingual pedagogies in a credible way, that is, in a political context that members of the public can understand and endorse."

Furthermore, a number of different forms of bilingual education have been identified by Baker [1996], Thomas and Collier [1997], and Akkari [1998]. In their longitudinal study, Thomas and Collier [1997] identified a number of bilingual program types in USA and mapped their different educational effects on ESL students. They reported that ESL students who had been placed in different bilingual programs as elementary students fared considerably better in the long run. In such a linguistic environment, it is not surprising that an ambitious bilingual educational model such as immersion, geared for native speakers of Indonesian. The school operating English immersion program, Jambi Bilingual School(JBS), for example, offers English immersion from kindergarten through senior high school. Some private schools and kindergartens in Jambi have implemented immersion programs such Kanaan Global School, Stella Maris, and Town for Kids, all of which began operation in more than ten years or later.

Actually, this study was a formative evaluation of language policy at an independent school in Jambi (JBS) in Indonesia seeking to serve English- speaking for playgroup, kindergarten, elementary and secondary school students. The program, which has been existence since 2004 aims to provide an international education in a bilingual environment where learners are said to have an opportunity to become proficient in two languages, Indonesia and English. The main aim of this study is to arrive at an assessment of school's language policy by examining elements related to curriculum; learners' needs, programs and course goals, the selection materials and learning activities, administrators and teachers, and assessment

through the collection and analysis of qualitative data, especially for teachers' barriers in teaching contents of English as the language of instruction.

2. Methods

Mixed methods design was employed to gather the data within the CIPP model developed by Stufflebeam [1973b] helped to define objectives for program under evaluation [Fitzpatrick, Sanders, & Worthen, 2004]. In identifying types of mixed methods designs, model and approach commonly used in educational research have been advanced by Creswell and Clark [2011], the convergent parallel design was used in this study to collect both quantitative and qualitative data, merge the data, and use the result to understand the research problem. We gathered both quantitative and qualitative data and analyzed datasets separately, related the result from the analysis, and made interpretation whether the results supported or contradicted each other. Students from secondary level, and teachers with different educational background involved as the participants in this study. Furthermore, demographic background information, questionnaire, and in-depth face to face interview were used in collecting the data. In serving qualitative data, the interview data were analyzed by using the constant comparative method developed by Glaser and Strauss [1967] as cited in Mukminin [2014]. All the transcripts among those participants will be analyzed and compared to search similarities and differences. While in serving quantitative data, descriptive statistics by using frequency distribution will be used to describe data from the questionnaire administered to teachers and students.

3. Findings and Discussions

Quantitative Data

This section presents the quantitative data obtained from closed and open- ended questionnaire. From teachers in general, first, all teachers noted that both native- students and non- native students that they teach were placed at the right level. Second, when they were asked how well teaching materials matched the skill level of native- speaking students and non- native speaking students, three teachers noticed 'well', a teacher noticed 'very well', and a teacher noticed "quite well". Third, concerning on oral proficiency level in English, three teachers considered that they were in elementary level, while the rest were in beginner level. Fourth, relating to the proportion of instructional both English and Indonesian, three teachers who had educational background of English, they used English 50% and Indonesian 50%, while other teachers used high proportion of Indonesian- medium instruction, those problems caused three teachers used English well during the class, whereas two teachers who did not have educational background of English did not use English enough during the class. Finally, the issue of rate progression level of native- speaking students in the class, all teachers stated 'satisfy' with their progress. Meanwhile, a teacher noted 'very satisfy' when she was asked relating to rate progression level of non- native speaking students in the class.

Furthermore, in terms' of students' perception, The respondents to the question "Are your textbook easy to understand?" clearly prefer dominantly "yes" (74.5 %) for English, Religion, Science, Computer, Civics, Social Studies, Art and Culture, Bahasa Indonesia, and Physical Exercise subjects. While for Mandarin subjects, they prefer dominantly "No" (25.5 %). It means that most students for eleven subjects understand the textbooks easily aside from Mandarin subject. Based on the result administered to students (question 2), the teachers who teach in academic and non- academic subjects showed a stronger preference by using Indonesian teaching the class for Religion, Computer, Civics, Art and Culture, Bahasa Indonesia, and Physical Exercise subjects as 64.9 %. In other subject such English, there was a very strong preference for teachers by using English as 63.88 %. While students' responses (respondents) indicated more desire

for bilingual especially for Math, Science, Social Studies, and local content subject (Culinary and Jambi Culture) as 26.5 %. Responding to question 3 administered to students, as 47.7 % respondent affirmed “Yes, I do” being asked whether they understand or not what the teachers say even in English, and as 7.32 % affirmed that they did not understand what the teachers say, even in English, particularly in terms of ‘Culinary and Jambi Culture’ subject. While as 44.95% of respondents considered that the teachers prefer to speak Indonesia when they explain the material of each subject.

As for students’ views, students’ responses to the question ‘Are you able to get enough help from teacher (s) when you have trouble understanding the lesson or the textbook?, are divided into three respondents rating; “Yes”, “No”, and “I don’t need help”. The number who rated “yes” was greater than the number who rated “No” (47.7 % > 7.32%). And as 44.95 % of respondents rated as “I don’t need help”. In addition, question 5 in the questionnaire asked students’ views in whether they thought they were learning enough English. Among respondents, nearly most students indicated that they felt they were learning enough English grammar, reading, and writing as 79.63 %, while as 24.07 % of respondents noticed that they do not learn English enough. Responding to question 7, regarding whether they wanted more classes taught in English, Indonesian, or bilingually. Surprisingly, more than a half respondents were opposed to having more of their classes taught in English as 63.88 %, and others (a half respondents) desired more classes to be taught in Indonesian as 50 %. About three fourths of respondents also indicated a desire for more bilingual instruction as 66.67 %.

4. Qualitative Data

Barriers of Using English Instruction

Currently, the implementation process is encountering many challenges that ranges from teachers’ attitude to language policy, to material resources implementing the policy, and to teacher training and professional development, students, teachers, supervisor as the controller, and facility. Therefore, to identify the particular barriers of using English instruction in JBS, we figured out seven themes based in equitation majority teachers’ perspectives as the participants. As presented in table 1, seven salient themes and their sub- themes emerged from the individual interview in the following.

Table 1. Themes and Sub-themes

Themes	Sub- themes
1. Teachers’ attitude to language policy	Positive: Having great enthusiasm with bilingualism <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Use English fully both in classroom and outside of classroom Negative: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Feeling “comfort” at best indifferent- There is “unwilling” feeling.- Use English only for instruction and opening the class.

2. Material resources	<p>Students' confused on materials in terms of teaching methods</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Difficult to understand on My pals textbooks. -
3. Teacher training and professional development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of awareness/ willingness to maintain the bilingualism - lack of professional development of teachers (training) - Lack of certificated teachers - No systematic teacher training - A few teachers specialized in English
4. Students	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Having no willingness to speak English (They can but they do not want) - Bad influence from other friends
5. Teachers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of English oral proficiency - Only having one certificated teachers - Having better choice (passing the scholarships and civil servant test) - Preferring to be "silent" rather than speak up regarding the bilingualism issue
6. Supervisor as the controller	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lost control from controller to maintain English development - Inconsistent in implementing the policy
7. Facility	Lack of teachers' room.

To relate the school's language policy is implemented and its affect on learning, the barriers presented by the linguistic environment with a number of internal negative factors. First, there is no general curriculum for ESL program provided by school for native speakers (Indonesian). Consequently, there were no clear goals and objectives for any grade- level. It is not surprising that such varying degrees of satisfactions were expressed by both native and non- native students of English regarded to learning the language. It is needed to set a well- structured curriculum in terms of specific goals and objectives for each class in order to have clear directions from teachers to achieve specific targets. It will be very useful to develop strong English skills [Bostwick, 1999].

Moreover, the lack of tight guidelines to regulate the proportion of classes taught in English, Indonesian, or bilingually has hindered English development in implementing language policy. Based on the interview data, a disproportional of the instructional language of classes being taught in Indonesian in secondary level students was reported by some teachers. They stated that they use English only for greeting and asking questions, they do not use it enough for explaining the material. They admitted that they could not fully use English because they may not be proficient in the language [Haryanto, 2013]. Therefore, they did not implement the policy and fully aware that they are not proficient in English, besides that it is difficult to deliver the content subjects through English. Thus, the result of this study affirms a common finding in

terms of the instructional language used by teachers in bilingual schools [Moulden, 2005; Haryanto, 2013]. Besides, particularly for non- native speakers of English, the use of Indonesian mostly spoken by teachers to explain the important concepts, has removed the students' needs to focus on bilingualism. It is incompatible with the school's general goals and limits their opportunities fluent in bilingualism.

Focusing the materials chosen by the school, the issue of textbooks and their influence on language development goes beyond those materials used has created some difficulties for non- native students of English. This is the other negative factor hindering English- language development. My pals are Here (A textbook series from Singapore), based on the findings, it could be identified that students felt confused, especially the textbooks for Mathematics and Science written in English. Some students experienced difficulties with the material needed to ask for individual assistance in English unless they could receive help from classmates. This finding is in line for ESL students in Japan [Bostwick, 1999]. Even though a teacher thought that the materials matched students well in terms of difficulty. However, for those who have lack of English proficiency and inexperience, they considered the materials to be "difficult" for non-native students of Indonesia understanding the content. Thus, they have put non- native students of English at risk linguistically and academically.

Further, from the point of view of bilingual teachers who are very well aware of this policy, the school and the government intervention in their language practices may lead to disloyalty due to their lack of English proficiency. In case of JBS, the problem is that some teachers spoke a language (Indonesian) mostly as one of the major components of the Indonesian cultural heritage. It does not really refer to any official document where it was recorded. Moreover, it is a policy that has been marked by lack of planning prior to the crafting of the policy itself. This finding is very consistent with the study in Marocco conducted by Errihani [2007]. He added that the school needs to act quickly before the situation can get out of control, and the result can provide a short term solution to a serious and long term situation.

In short, it is important to point out that this study was a formative rather than summative evaluation in JBS with regard to language policy. The main goal of the school policy is to be competence in both languages; English and Indonesian. JBS, therefore, does not have two- way, or dual language, immersion program, as defined by Baker [2002]. In fact, such a program is not really practical given the linguistic composition of the student body in JBS, such no effort to ensure that there are exactly numbers of English hours of each subject in any class. This is not to suggest that this program is ineffective, the current structure of English hours will help to facilitate teaching and learning in some respects.

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

To conclude, the design of secondary school program cannot be fully understood or evaluated except in light of the elementary and senior high school program. Even though English language development is emphasized in secondary program at some expense to Indonesian, a stronger focus in Indonesian rather than English. Further, we should mention that the situation in JBS is rather complex due to some important implications regarding such matters as recruitment of personnel such an experienced principal, English program director, and teachers with relevant training and experience, and selection of teaching material (more suitable core textbook series).

As a bilingual education or a bilingual school, it offers an opportunity for researchers to study further development research in terms of bilingual itself in JBS or other areas; (1) conduct a longitudinal study by monitoring students' English linguistic development and their academic achievement in English, (2) examine the effect of the English proficiency on Indonesian by administering the standardized test for

secondary student levels, and (3) compare the English proficiency of Indonesian students at the same grade level in order to examine where the differences exist between groups.

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